

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Aloe vera and garlic ameliorate thermoxidized palm oil-induced haemostatic derangement in albino Wistar rats

A. U. Ime*, E. J. Ani, V. U. Nna, C. E. Obeten

Department of Physiology, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Medical Sciences, University of Calabar, P.M.B. 1115, Calabar, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: Akaninyene Ubong Ime; E-mail: akaninyeneime1@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of *Aloe vera* and garlic on haemostatic status of rats fed thermoxidized palm oil diet (TPO). 35 male Wistar rats (140-170 grams) used in this study were randomly assigned five groups (n=7): Control, TPO, TPO + garlic juice (TPO+G), TPO + Aloe gel (TPO+A) and TPO + garlic/Aloe gel (TPO+G+A). TPO diet was prepared by mixing 85 g of rat chow with 15 g of thermoxidized oil. The juice and gel were orally administered at doses of 2 ml/kg and 6 ml/kg respectively. After three months, the rats were sacrificed and blood collected through cardiac puncture for analysis. Plasma fibrinogen was significantly ($P<0.001$) reduced in TPO group compared to Control, whereas, fibrinogen increased in all treated groups. Platelet count was significantly ($P<0.001$) decreased in TPO compared with control. Platelet count was significantly decreased ($P<0.001$) in TPO+G compared to TPO and control, but significantly ($P<0.001$) increased in TPO+A, and TPO+G+A compared to TPO. Prothrombin and clotting times were significantly increased ($P<0.001$) in TPO and TPO+G compared to control. Bleeding time was significantly increased ($P<0.001$) in TPO compared to control, but significantly reduced in TPO+A compared to TPO. Chronic consumption of TPO has deleterious haemostatic by reducing plasma fibrinogen, platelet count and causing an increase in prothrombin, clotting and bleeding times. However, these debilitating effects were seen to be markedly ameliorated following separate and combined administrations of *Aloe vera* gel and garlic juice. Additionally, *Aloe vera* gel seemed to have a more significant effect compared with garlic juice.

Keywords: Garlic; *Aloe vera*; Thermoxidized palm oil; Haemostatic status; Platelet; Fibrinogen.

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Ime AU, Ani EJ, Nna VU, Obeten CE. *Aloe vera* and garlic ameliorate thermoxidized palm oil-induced haemostatic derangement in albino Wistar rats. MicroMed. 2017; 5(2): 53-59.

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.839688>

Received: June 01, 2017

Revised: July 25, 2017

Accepted: August 04, 2017

Copyright: © 2017 Ime AU, et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

www.journals.tmkarpinski.com/index.php/mmed

Transparency declaration: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical considerations: permission was granted by the ethical committee of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria (approval number 18/17).

INTRODUCTION

Thermoxidized palm oil, derived from fresh palm oil of *Elaeis guineensis* fruit is widely used as cooking oil in Nigeria and other parts of the world. The oil is thermoxidized when its fresh form is subjected to several rounds of heating at high temperatures [1]. Chronic consumption of TPO diet has been implicated in several ailments in the body such as cardiovascular, haematological diseases, reproductive dysfunction, thrombosis,

fatty livers, essential fatty acids deficiency and micronutrient malnutrition leading to deactivation of key metabolic enzymes [2-9].

Thermoxidation negatively affects most vegetable oils, thus, inducing alterations in their chemical properties when compared to the nutritionally healthy fresh form [10]. Thermoxidation of palm oil has been reported to be the root cause of most deleterious consequences associated with consumption of palm oil diets [5]. This results from formation of peroxides and increased free radical generation known to be highly reactive, cytotoxic and destructive to tissues [2, 3].

Plants derived natural substances; some of which are antioxidants have captured great interest due to their numerous therapeutic importances like scavenging free radicals. Proximate analysis of *Aloe vera* and garlic has revealed the presence of several bioactive compounds with different medicinal efficacies. Allicin, a thiosulfinate extract of garlic has been reported to possess strong antioxidant properties [11]. Treatment with *Aloe vera* gel has been presumed to reduce lipid peroxidation levels, increases the levels of some antioxidant enzymes (SOD, CAT and GPx) including glutathione [12]. Several health benefits of *Aloe vera* and garlic exist in literatures [13-17].

In view of the increasing incidence of complications associated with TPO consumption, research on remedies which are cheap and potent in preventing these ailments is desirable and expedient. Due to their therapeutic effects, this study was therefore aimed at investigating if both garlic and *Aloe vera* which are readily available and affordable could help prevent or ameliorate the devastating effects attributable to thermoxidized palm oil diet consumption.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials and extraction

Garlic cloves were purchased from Watt Market while *Aloe vera* was collected from a domestic garden located in Uwanse street, all in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The authentication of the plant materials was done by a botanist in the Department of Botany, University of Calabar, Nigeria.

Garlic cloves were washed, thinly sliced and blended for 25 minutes using electric blender to extract the natural juice. The blended mixture was then left to stand for 10 minutes in order to allow a total enzymatic reaction of alliin with allinase [18]. The mixture was first filtered using filter paper and filtered again with a syringe filter to ensure that no garlic particles would obstruct the column. *Aloe vera* leaves were thoroughly washed with clean tepid water to remove dirt. The base of the leaves was cut off with surgical blades and these were sliced open along the margin to reveal the transparent mucilage. The transparent mucilage was carefully scooped into a beaker with the aid of a spatula. The gel was then homogenized using an electric blender for 10 minutes. This was allowed for 20 minutes and afterwards sieved using Whatman filter paper to obtain a particulate-free gel [19]. Garlic and Aloe extracts were preserved in the refrigerator (at temperatures between 4-6^oC) for three days in the research laboratory of the Department of Physiology, University of Calabar, Calabar, after each day's use.

Preparation of thermoxidized palm oil diet

Fresh palm oil was purchased from Mbukpa Market, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. The fresh oil was thermally oxidized by heating the oil at 150°C in a stainless steel pot intermittently for five times at about 20 minutes for each round of heating [2]. After each round, the thermoxidized oil was allowed to cool for five hours. TPO diet was prepared by mixing 85 g of rat chow with 15 g of cooled thermoxidized palm oil as used in previous studies [1, 20, 21].

Experimental animals and protocol

Thirty five male Wistar rats weighing 140-170 grams were purchased from the Department of Physiology, University of Calabar, Calabar. They were randomly assigned into five groups (n = 7), namely; control, TPO – fed group, TPO+garlic juice group, TPO+A group and TPO+G+A group. This was done after permission was granted by the ethical committee of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria on the use of experimental animals for scientific purposes with approval number 18/17. Garlic juice and *Aloe vera* gel were orally administered at doses of 2 ml/kg and 6 ml/kg, respectively (the safe dose taken as 1/3 of the LD₅₀) from the result for lethality studies as reported by Ime et al. [22].

The animals were kept in clean cages in the animal house of the Department of Physiology for one week, for acclimatization, before feeding and administration for three months. The control and TPO groups were also given oral administration of normal saline at 6 ml/kg body weight, thus exposing all the groups to the same physiological condition. All animals had access to feed and water *ad libitum* while the juice and gel were given via oral route administration.

After three months of administration and feeding, the rats were allowed an overnight fast before sacrifice. In line with the guidelines of the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate animals used for scientific purposes, they were anaesthetized with chloroform and afterwards their thorax were opened and blood collected via cardiac puncture with sterile syringe into EDTA sample bottles to obtain serum for analysis.

Determination of plasma fibrinogen

Plasma fibrinogen concentration was determined as defined by the clot weight method, though with modifications to accommodate the procedure for use of thrombin time (TT) test kit as given by the manufacturers of the kit [23]. Blood was collected with the aid of plastic disposable syringes into sample vials containing 3.2% sodium citrate in the ratio 1:9 with blood. Blood plasma was obtained by centrifuging blood in a stopped vial at 1000 g for 10 min. 0.2 ml of the test plasma was put into a test tube and incubated in a water bath for 3 min at 37°C. 0.2 ml of thrombin time-reagent was added to test plasma, mixed and the clot formed harvested with a wooden applicator stick. The resulting clot was transferred into a tube containing acetone to dry and harden for about 10 min; the acetone was decanted and the clot placed on a filter paper for the remaining acetone to evaporate. The clot was then recovered and weighed. The process of fibrinogen concentration determination was completed within 3 h of blood collection. Thus, fibrinogen concentration of citrated plasma in mg/dl equals clot weight (mg) divided by plasma volume (dl).

Determination of bleeding time

The time elapsed the moment of escape of blood outside the vessel and the moment of cessation of the flow is known as bleeding time. Bleeding time was determined by Duke's method [24].

The tail of albino Wistar rat was cleaned with methylated spirit and allowed to dry. A quick deep prick with a lancet was made in the tail resulting in blood flowing out and the time noted. With a filter paper, the blood was dabbed every half a minute using a fresh part of the filter paper for each touch. It was noted that the blood spots on the filter paper gets smaller till it disappears when bleeding stops and the blood spots counted and the number divided by two giving the bleeding time in minutes.

Determination of clotting time by Wright's capillary method

This was determined by Wright Capillary method [25]. The tail of albino Wistar rat was cleaned with methylated spirit and allowed to dry. A quick deep prick with a lancet was made in the tail resulting in blood flowing out. This was drained immediately into the capillary tube by placing one end of the capillary tube on the drop of the blood. The capillary tube was tilted downwards so that the blood can easily flow into the tube.

When the capillary tube (10 cm nearly) was more or less filled, it was removed. After about two minutes, small lengths of the tube were snapped off at 30 seconds interval. Initially, the blood column broke easily and cleanly. At the end point, a thick strand or coagulated blood column was seen stretching between the broken ends and the time noted. It is important to break the tube gently without jerking the ends apart or else the strand will be snapped by the movement before it is observed. Normal clotting time by this method is about three to eight minutes.

Estimation of prothrombin time

0.1 ml of plasma was delivered into the bottom of a 75×10 mm tube in a water bath at 37°C and 0.1 ml of thromboplastin added to it. After a delay of about one minute, 0.1 ml of warmed 0.025 M calcium chloride was added and the contents of the tube were carefully mixed. A stop watch was started and the tube was held with its lower end submerged. The tube was continuously but gently inclined from the vertical to just short off the horizontal so that its contents can be observed for the first signs of clotting. A fibrin clot developing within a second marked the end point. The test was repeated thrice and the average reading was taken [26].

Statistical analysis

The data obtained was analyzed by one way ANOVA of the SPSS statistical program and post hoc tests (LSD) between groups using Microsoft (MS) excel program and the result presented as mean ± SEM. P value of less than 0.05 was accepted as statistically significant.

RESULTS

Comparison of platelet count in the different experimental groups

Platelet count was significantly reduced ($P<0.001$) in TPO when compared to control. More so, TPO+G induced a marked significant reduction ($P<0.001$, $P<0.05$, $P<0.001$ and $P<0.001$) in Platelet count compared to control, TPO, TPO+A, and TPO+G+A respectively. However, TPO+A, and TPO+G+A caused a progressive significant increase ($P<0.001$) in platelet count when compared to TPO and TPO+garlic (Table 1).

Comparison of plasma fibrinogen in the different experimental groups

Plasma fibrinogen level was significantly reduced ($P<0.001$) in TPO compared to control. Though Fibrinogen was also reduced in the three treated group, but there was progressively increase in all treated groups when compared to TPO. Meanwhile, TPO+A induced a tremendous significant increase ($P<0.001$) in plasma fibrinogen level when compared to TPO+G and TPO+G+A (Table 1).

Comparison of prothrombin time in the different experimental groups

Prothrombin time was significantly increased ($P<0.001$) in all four groups when compared to control. Meanwhile, there was a progressive significant decrease ($P<0.05$, $P<0.001$ and $P<0.001$) in prothrombin time of TPO+G, TPO+A and TPO+G+A when compared to TPO respectively (Table 1).

Comparison of clotting time in the different experimental groups

There was a significant increase ($P<0.001$) of clotting time in all four experimental groups compared to control. However, clotting time was significantly decreased ($P<0.001$) in TPO+A when compared to TPO, TPO+G and TPO+G+A (Table 1)

Comparison of bleeding time in the different experimental groups

A significant increase ($P < 0.001$) was observed in bleeding time of TPO, TPO+G and TPO+G+A compared to control. However, TPO+A significantly decreased ($P < 0.001$) bleeding time when compared to TPO, TPO+G and TPO+G+A (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of haemostatic parameters in the different experimental groups

Variables	Groups				
	Control	TPO	TPO+G	TPO+A	TPO+G+A
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/l$)	606.7 \pm 22.1	433.7 \pm 8.3 ^{***}	393.6 \pm 7.8 ^{***, a}	549.9 \pm 10.7 ^{***, c, f}	501.1 \pm 11.6 ^{***, c, f, y}
Fibrinogen level (g/dl)	213.7 \pm 4.7	102.1 \pm 8.7 ^{***}	114.3 \pm 9.0 ^{***, a, z}	176.3 \pm 10.7 ^{***, c}	153.6 \pm 12.8 ^{***, c, z}
Prothrombin time (seconds)	9.4 \pm 0.4	15.7 \pm 0.2 ^{***}	14.7 \pm 0.3 ^{***, a}	12.7 \pm 0.2 ^{***, c, f}	11.9 \pm 0.3 ^{***, c, f, x}
Clotting time (seconds)	3.7 \pm 0.1	9.0 \pm 0.2 ^{***, z}	8.5 \pm 0.3 ^{***, z}	5.1 \pm 0.2 ^{***}	6.7 \pm 0.3 ^{***, c, f, z}
Bleeding time (seconds)	8.7 \pm 0.3	13.3 \pm 0.3 ^{***}	11.9 \pm 0.4 ^{***, b}	8.7 \pm 0.3 ^{c, f}	10.2 \pm 0.3 ^{***, c, f, z}

Values are mean \pm Standard deviation

* $p < 0.05$ vs Control; ** $p < 0.01$ vs Control; *** $p < 0.001$ vs Control

a = $p < 0.05$ vs TPO; b = $p < 0.01$ vs TPO; c = $p < 0.001$ vs TPO

d = $p < 0.05$ vs TPO+Garlic; e = $p < 0.01$ vs TPO+Garlic; f = $p < 0.001$ vs TPO+Garlic

x = $p < 0.05$ vs TPO+Aloe; z = $y < 0.01$ vs TPO+Aloe; z = $p < 0.001$ vs TPO+Aloe.

DISCUSSION

The platelet count was significantly reduced in TPO group compared to control. It was however found that garlic treated group caused a greater reduction in platelet count compared to TPO diet fed group. Interestingly, platelet count was significantly increased in TPO+Aloe vera group compared to TPO group although it was significantly less than control. Platelet count was significantly increased in TPO+garlic+aloe group compared to TPO group although less than TPO+Aloe vera group. Several reports have established decrease platelet count induced by TPO [1, 20, 27].

Platelets are synthesized in the bone marrow by fragmentation of the cytoplasm of a group of cells called megakaryocytes which arise by a process of cell differentiation from the haemopoietic stem cell [28]. From the result, it is likely that there exist constituent(s) in *Aloe vera* that help ameliorate the devastating effect caused by TPO on blood. *Aloe vera* is known to be highly rich in antioxidants that could help mop up the free radicals associated with TPO. From the result, garlic is seen to worsen the effect caused by TPO on platelet. It is therefore likely that garlic may either be harmful to haemopoietic stem cells or committed platelet progenitors that give rise to platelets or on mature platelets themselves although the exact mechanism was not studied in this research. Garlic has been reported to inhibit platelet aggregation which could affect haemostasis [29].

Bleeding, clotting and prothrombin time were all markedly increased in TPO fed rats and garlic treated group compared to control. However, these parameters witnessed a great progressive decrease in *Aloe vera* treated group. Bleeding, clotting and prothrombin time are markers of haemostatic status in which clotting factors play important role. While clotting time is the measure of intrinsic pathway, prothrombin time measures the extrinsic pathway [29]. Therefore, clotting time measures the functions of factors: I, II, V, VIII, IX, X, XI and XII whereas prothrombin time indicates the functions of factors: III, V, VII and X. These factors are mostly

synthesized in the liver. It is therefore possible that TPO has adverse effect on the function of the liver either through free radical damage to liver cells or mechanisms that are yet to be established. The increase in bleeding time could be attributed to antiplatelet effect of garlic as seen from the result of this study and its reported interaction with warfarin [28].

The mechanism through which *Aloe vera* reduces clotting and bleeding time is yet unknown but from the result of this research, it could be attributable to its marked increase in fibrinogen although this is in contrast with a research work [30] which reported a dose dependent decrease in prothrombin, clotting and fibrinogen following administration of *Aloe vera* gel on alternative days for 14 days. This variation may have resulted from the difference in duration of administration.

Plasma fibrinogen level was greatly reduced in TPO fed rats. However, *Aloe vera* and garlic proved to be potent in reversing this effect. Many plasma proteins including fibrinogen are synthesized by the liver. Amino acids, which are the building blocks for synthesis of proteins, are necessary to maintain adequate supply of these substrates for such liver synthetic function. From this study, it is likely that garlic and *Aloe vera* improves liver integrity by supplying substrates for its synthetic function or improves upon the integrity of gastrointestinal tract for absorption of nutrients as reported [31, 32].

The results of this study have shown that chronic consumption of TPO has deleterious effects on haemostatic status of Wistar rats by reducing plasma fibrinogen, platelet count and causing an increase in prothrombin, clotting and bleeding times. However, these debilitating effects were seen to be markedly ameliorated following garlic juice and *Aloe vera* gel administration. If these results are to be applicable to humans, then the chronic consumption of thermoxidized palm oil diet should be seriously discouraged.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

This research was carried out by four authors. EJA designed the study. This research and laboratory work was done by AUI with the assistance of CEO. Data analysis was carried out by VUN while AUI interpreted and wrote the article. EJA read and corrected the initial draft before the manuscript was submitted. The final manuscript was read and approved by all authors.

REFERENCES

1. Ani EJ, Nna VU, Okon UA, Ekpenyong CE. Effect of *Aloe vera* gel on thermoxidized palm oil induced derangements in some haematological and biochemical parameters. *Pharmacia Lettre*. 2014; 6(6): 448-452.
2. Osim EE, Owu DU, Isong EU, Umoh IB. Influence of chronic consumption of thermoxidized palm oil diet on platelet aggregation in the rat. *Discov Innov*. 1992; 4: 83-87.
3. Owu DU, Osim EE, Ebong PE. Serum liver enzymes profile of Wistar rats following chronic consumption of fresh or oxidized palm oil diets. *Acta Trop*. 1998; 69(1): 65-73.
4. Isong EU, Essien EU, Eka OU, Umoh IB. Sex-and organ-specific toxicity in normal and malnourished rats fed thermoxidized palm oil. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 2000; 38(11): 997-1004.
5. Edem DO. Palm oil: Biochemical, physiological, nutritional, hematological and toxicological aspects: A review. *Plant Foods Human Nutr*. 2002; 57(3): 319-341.
6. Mesembe OE, Ibanga I, Osim EE. The effects of fresh and thermoxidized palm oil diets on some haematological indices in the rat. *Niger J Physiol Sci*. 2005; 19(1): 86-91.
7. Obembe AO, Okwari OO, Owu DU, Antai AB, Osim EE. Intestinal motility and transit following chronic ingestion of different forms of palm oil diets. *Niger J Physiol Sci*. 2008; 23(1-2): 95-99.
8. Adam SK, Das S, Jaarin K. A detailed microscopic study of the changes in the aorta of experimental model of postmenopausal rats fed with repeatedly heated palm oil. *Int J Exp Pathol*. 2009; 90(3): 321-327.
9. Leong XF, Najib MN, Das S, Mustafa MR, Jaarin K. Intake of repeatedly heated palm oil causes elevation in blood pressure with impaired vasorelaxation in rats. *Tohoku J Exp Med*. 2009; 219(1): 71-78.
10. Ng TK. What food for the heart? *World Health Forum*. 1997; 18: 196-198.

11. Chan JY, Yuen AC, Chan RY, Chan SW. A review of the cardiovascular benefits and antioxidant properties of allicin. *Phytother Res.* 2013; 27(5): 637-646.
12. Anilakumar KR, Sudarshanakrishna KR, Chandramohan G, Ilaiyaraja N, Khanum F, Bawa AS. Effect of *Aloe vera* gel extract on antioxidant enzymes and azoxymethane-induced oxidative stress in rats. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 2010; 48(8): 837.
13. Christaki EV, Florou-Paneri PC. *Aloe vera*: a plant for many uses. *J Food Agric Environ.* 2010; 8(2): 245-249.
14. Rodriguez ER, Martin JD, Romero CD. *Aloe vera* as a functional ingredient in foods. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2010; 50(4): 305-326.
15. Hannan A, Ullah MI, Usman M, Hussain S, Absar M, Javed K. Anti-mycobacterial activity of garlic (*Allium sativum*) against multi-drug resistant and non-multi-drug resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Pak J Pharmac Sci.* 2011; 24(1): 81-85.
16. Khayatnouri M, Bahari K, Safarmashaei S. Study of the effect of gliclazide and garlic extract on blood sugar level in STZ-induced diabetic male mice. *Adv Environ Biol.* 2011; 5(7): 1751-1756.
17. Mohammadi A, Oshaghi EA. Effect of garlic on lipid profile and expression of LXR alpha in intestine and liver of hypercholesterolemic mice. *J Diab Metab Disord.* 2014; 13(1): 1.
18. Chowdhury R, Dutta A, Chaudhuri SR, Sharma N, Giri AK, Chaudhuri K. In vitro and in vivo reduction of sodium arsenite induced toxicity by aqueous garlic extract. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2008; 46: 740-751.
19. Ani EJ, Ibu IO, Ofem OE. Gastric acid secretion induced by *Aloe barbadensis* (*Aloe vera*) gel. *West Afr J Biol Sci.* 2005; 16: 15-24.
20. Mesembe OE, Ibanga I, Osim EE. The effects of fresh and thermoxidized palm oil diets on some haematological indices in the rat. *Niger J Physiol Sci.* 2004; 19(1-2): 86-91.
21. Ani EJ, Nna VU, Obi CE, Udobong, NJ. Comparative effects of thermoxidized palm oil and groundnut oil diets on some haematological parameters in albino wistar rats. *Austral J Basic Appl Sci.* 2015; 9: 181-184.
22. Ime AU, Ani EJ, Nna VU, Obeten CE. *Aloe vera* and garlic ameliorate deleterious consequences of thermoxidized palm oil diet on liver function and histology in rat. *J Nutr Food Sci.* 2016; 46 (6): 803-815.
23. Ingram GI. A suggested schedule for the rapid determination of acute haemostatic failure. *J Clin Pathol.* 1961; 14: 356-360.
24. Duke WW. The relation of blood platelets to hemorrhagic disease: description of a method for determining the bleeding time and coagulation time and report of three cases of hemorrhagic disease relieved by transfusion. *J Am Med Assoc.* 1910; 55(14): 1185-1192.
25. Wright RL, Kowada M, Thurston JM, Majno G. Cerebral ischemia. II. The no-reflow phenomenon. *Am J Pathol.* 1968; 52(2): 437.
26. Ochei J, Kolhatkar A. *Medical laboratory science: theory and practice.* 2nd edn. New Delhi: McGraw-Hill, 2000: 331-349.
27. Okwari OO, Emerole CG, Dasofunjo K, Ezugwu HC, Obi J. Haematological profile of rats administered with aqueous leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera* following thermoxidized palm oil diet induced toxicity. *J Pharm Biol Sci.* 2014; 9: 41-45.
28. Hoffbrand AV, Moss, PA. *Essential haematology.* 6th edn. John Wiley and Sons, London, UK, 2008.
29. Hogg J. *Garlic supplements. Complementary medicines summary.* UK Medicines Information, National Health Service, 2007.
30. Dapper DV, Achinike PN, Gwotmut MD. The effects of *Aloe vera* gel clotting time, prothrombin time and plasma fibrinogen concentration in albino Wistar rats. *Portharcourt Med J.* 2007; 2: 56-60.
31. Igiri AO, Ibeghu AO, Osim EE. The morphological and histological changes in the small intestine induced by chronic consumption of palm oil diets in rats. *Trop J Appl Sci.* 1994; 384: 144-153.
32. Jones W, Goebel RJ. *Garlic and health. Vegetables, fruits, and herbs in health promotion.* Boca Raton: CRC Press. 2001: 205-216.